
Handbook for know-how to stakeholders on Early warning in case of floods

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IMPETUS

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Abbreviations

CP - *Civil Protection*

DBMS - *Database Management System*

DSM - *Digital Surface Model*

DTM - *Digital Terrain Model*

EU - *European Union*

EWS - *Early warning system*

GDPR - *General Data Protection Regulation*

GIS - *Geographic Information System*

GPS - *Global Positioning System*

HEC-RAS - *Hydrologic Engineering Centre River Analysis System*

HR - *Human Resources*

IMPD - *Infrastructure Maintenance and Projects Department*

IT - *Information technology*

JCMI - *Jelgava City Municipality Institution*

JDC - *Jelgava Digital Centre*

JREB - *Jelgava Real Estate Board*

JSC - *Joint-Stock Company*

JUICS - *Jelgava Unified Information Circulation System*

LEGMC - *Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre*

Ltd. - *Limited Liability Company*

MOIC - *Municipal Operational Information Centre*

MVT - *Map Vector Tiles*

RBD - *River Basin District*

RKB - *Resilience Knowledge Boosters*

SFRS - *State Fire and Rescue Service*

WEB - *World Wide Web*

IMPETUS project

The Horizon 2020-funded project IMPETUS: Dynamic Information Management Approach for the Implementation of Climate Resilient Adaptation Packages in European Regions - was launched in October 2021.

Climate change is advancing rapidly and requires a swift response and effective measures to increase resilience and adaptive capacity. Effective, climate-resilient regions cannot be built at the expense of productive sectors or without a fair public consensus as a result of the Covid-19 crisis.

The project aims to accelerate Europe's response to climate change and translate commitments into concrete action by developing innovative measures to make its regions more resilient to climate change, and explores synergies between climate change mitigation, supporting regional socio-economic growth and stability, and the transition of communities towards ecological sustainability and resilience.

The IMPETUS project assessed and developed a coherent multi-level, cross-sectoral framework for climate change adaptation to accelerate the transition to a climate-neutral and sustainable economy. The IMPETUS *Resilience Knowledge Boosters* (RKB, available at: <https://impetus.mantisims.gr/knowledge-boosters/>) will build a strong community of stakeholders, supported by reliable data and assessment methods to support decision-making and policy-making. As a result, the community will be able to jointly develop, assess, deploy and monitor climate adaptation innovation packages, including methodological, technological, governance, comprehension, behavioural, economic, financial and pathway components of research and innovation.

The IMPETUS consortium consists of selected local, regional and national authorities; research and development organisations; small, medium and large enterprises and international organisations to improve and demonstrate a wide range of research and development solutions. The project lead partner is the technology research centre EURECAT. The project partners in Latvia are the Baltic Environmental Forum, the Zemgale Planning Region and the Jelgava Digital Centre.

The project implementation period is from 01.10.2021. to 31.12.2025.

Summary

The Handbook is a guide that provides guidelines for the implementation, maintenance and management of an Early warning system in cases of flood risks. It is intended to provide users with a common understanding and knowledge base on the operation of the system, ensuring the notification process, and the areas of responsibility of the parties involved. The manual evaluates the processes that are implemented in the Jelgava Digital Centre, a municipal institution of the state city of Jelgava.

Since the Municipal Operational Information Centre (hereinafter referred to as MOIC) of the Jelgava Digital Centre is an essential mechanism for ensuring the early warning process, the Handbook particularly emphasizes its importance and the possibility of replication in different municipalities. MOIC ensures centralized information exchange, processing of warnings and their dissemination to residents, which allows for effective coordination of actions and timely response to risks. The Handbook also includes guidelines for MOIC replication, describing the necessary processes, involved human resources and their competencies, explaining the management, cooperation and competency requirements that must be taken into account when implementing MOIC in different municipalities and ensuring its integration into the Early warning system.

To explain the functioning of the Early warning system, the Handbook describes the basic principles of the system architecture, provides information on the minimum technical requirements for testing and production environments, indicating how parameters can be adjusted according to the functionality and development capabilities of the system. Special attention is also paid to the role of the HEC-RAS program in the development of hydraulic flood models, which is an essential tool for accurate risk assessment and ensuring the operation of the Early warning system.

We hope that by familiarizing with the information provided in the Handbook, specialists will gain an idea of the establishment and operation of the Early warning system – from human resource recruitment and institutional cooperation to technical requirements of system and information circulation processes. We believe that the knowledge provided in the Handbook will allow specialists to develop and implement the effective Early warning system that will help respond to flood risks in a timely manner, mitigate possible consequences and protect society.

1. Municipal Operational Information Centre

Jelgava Digital Centre (hereinafter referred to as JDC) is implementing the IMPETUS project (Nr. 101037084), within the framework of which an audit of the processes of the structural unit “Municipal Operational Information Centre” of the institution (hereinafter referred to as the assessment) was initiated. The aim of the assessment was to gather information on the activities of the structural unit in order to provide an opportunity for other interested parties (e.g. municipalities) to assess the need for a similar structural unit and to provide an idea of the resources required to establish and ensure the operation of such a structural unit. During the assessment, which took place from October to December 2023, interviews were conducted with employees involved in ensuring the core and support processes of MOIC, and processes were observed.

The Handbook includes information on the analyzed core and support processes of MOIC. The main process of MOIC can best be described by the following steps:

Figure 1. **Steps of the core process of MOIC**

The core business processes are reviewed at a medium level of detail, process maps have been prepared for easier perception of processes and facilitating the daily work of Data Operators. Processes related to civil protection and early warning are reviewed separately. Taking into account the nature of MOIC operations, a large role in the Handbook is assigned to the compilation of resources necessary for ensuring MOIC operations, the analysis of existing and necessary human resources, as well as the analysis of cooperation with various cooperation partners.

The assessment also includes information on the preparatory work necessary for MOIC replication, which is divided into three groups:

Figure 2. **Preparations for MOIC replication**

This section of the Handbook was prepared taking into account the activities of the MOIC directly, without taking into account the current activities, development prospects or development plans of the JDC.

2. MOIC main business and support processes

Scope of the provided service

The territory monitored and supported on a daily basis by MOIC is the administrative territory of the city of Jelgava. The total area of the Jelgava city is 60.3 km² and there are ~56,000 residents. The municipality of the city has made significant improvements to the city's infrastructure, which notably facilitates the ability of MOIC to provide support to the residents of the city of Jelgava. The total area monitored by MOIC includes 366 streets with a total length of 270 km, 143 km of stormwater drainage systems, 2 water level control stations, more than 800 video surveillance cameras, 223 traffic lights and power lines with a total length of 825 km.

3D flood zone modeling has been developed for the city of Jelgava, and a river water level control system has been established. An internal optical network has been built, which ensures continuous exchange of video surveillance camera data - MOIC is provided with unlimited real-time monitoring of important objects of the Jelgava city, which facilitates the processing of incoming applications. Access to GIS allows the MOIC Data operator to identify the responsible maintainer or manager of the object for which an application has been received. In the case of the Jelgava city, GIS contains information about all streets, sidewalks on them, electricity poles, utility networks and other important information, which significantly expands the capabilities of MOIC Data operators to provide support to residents by accepting their applications and re-directing them according to their affiliation.

2.1. MOIC main processes

The MOIC Data operator performs daily work duties primarily within the Jelgava Unified Information Circulation System (in Latvian - JVIAS). The MOIC main process could best be described with the following process steps:

Figure 3. **MOIC main process**

The core business processes of MOIC can be divided into several groups based on the logical grouping of processes. The summary of processes includes information about the core business process groups, information sources, information channels, and process topics. The process blocks contain high-level information about the main groups of process steps. The summary is shown in Figure 4 below.

MOIC OPERATIONAL GUIDELINES:

External legal and regulatory acts of the state and municipality
 Internal regulatory acts of the municipality and MOIC
 Customer service standards

Updated: 7/11/2025

Field	Source of information / process starting point:	Information receiving channels	Process topics	Process blocks					
Coordination of CP resources for the tasks of emergency services	State Fire and Rescue Service Head of the Civil Protection Commission	Radio In-person information Call	Transport Evacuation of residents; registration of evacuated residents; temporary accommodation; food; social care	Receiving information about required resources	Assigning tasks to the relevant service provider	Coordinating the activities of the relevant service provider in specific cases	Preparing reports upon request		
Training in the field of CP	Emergency services (currently only the State Fire and Rescue Service) Decision of the CP Commission Decision of the MOIC (Municipal Operational Information Centre) Head	Email Order	1) Training at CP facilities 2) Other CP related training Training on the Functioning of the CP Commission	Receiving information about planned training sessions and the initial training planning meeting	Sending notifications to pre - defined group of participants Training planning	Receiving detailed information from the State Fire and Rescue Service and the relevant CP facility owner Training	Participation in the training Recording observations; retrospective meetings Submitting observations; retrospective meetings		
Development of CP Documents	CP administration informs the City Council, the Council informs the Head of the Municipal Operational Information Centre (JDC), the JDC Head informs the MOIC (Municipal Operational Information Centre) Head	Resolution	CP plan War plan Contingency plans for municipal institutions	Maintenance/update of the list of CP Commission experts	Receiving the task	Information Collection	Development of documents in cooperation with other institutions	Document review for approval	- Submission of feedback to the task issuer regarding task completion
Other Activities / Processes within CP	Initiative of MOIC or decision of the CP Commission Maintenance of HRO CP cards	Email Call	Inspection Maintenance	Observation with drones for potential floods or other cases to obtain information					

Figure 4. *Summary of processes*

The Handbook describes the processes according to the actual actions performed by employees. When replicating MOIC functions, it is necessary to ensure that all Data Operators have a standardized approach to work and variations in the process are minimized.

The duties and actions of MOIC Data Operators can be divided into the following groups:

- 🔗 processes of receiving and forwarding information from residents, partners or monitoring solutions, depending on the topic of the report;
- 🔗 processes related to Civil Protection (hereinafter referred to as CP);
- 🔗 the early warning process;
- 🔗 MOIC-specific support processes;
- 🔗 Data Operator activities in JVIAS:
 - report registration;
 - activity creation;
 - the process of recording, commenting and closing activity execution;
 - activity status check;
 - notification process.

2.2. MOIC core operations and support processes related to early warning

Taking into account the location of MOIC - the territory of Jelgava city municipality, which is exposed to flood risk - early warning is an essential tool to ensure prompt information exchange with residents whose properties are located in certain areas. Several core activities and support processes of MOIC are related to early warning:

Table 1. *MOIC core activities and support processes related to early warning*

Process	Process goal	Process outcomes	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Notification of the CP Commission about the CP Commission meeting/ CP event	Ensure prompt transmission of information about the convening of the CP Commission / CP Commission members about the CP event	Identical information was promptly passed on to CP Commission members	* MOIC Contact Centre Data Operator * Head of MOIC * Head of JDC	* The State Fire and Rescue Service (SFRS) or other operational service that ensures the initial transfer of information to the head of the JDC or MOIC * CP Commission members * Experts (as needed) * Resident or cooperation partner (if reporting an event)

Process	Process goal	Process outcomes	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Maintenance and updating of the list of CP commission members	Ensure that, if necessary, information reaches the relevant members of the CP Commission	The current list of CP Commission members is available in the system	The current list of CP Commission members is available in the system * MOIC Contact Centre Data Operator * Head of MOIC * Head of JDC	* CP Commission Chairman and CP Commission members
Notifying or warning residents in case of potential threat	Send notification or warning information to residents of a specific geographical area about a potential threat and further action	Notified or warned residents registered in the specified geographical area	* MOIC Contact Centre Data Operator * Head of MOIC * Head of JDC	* Resident * Operational Services
Maintenance and testing of the notification system, training of employees to use it	Ensure that notification in case of threat can be made at any time	The tool is available at any time, employees know how to use it	* MOIC Contact Centre Data Operator * Infrastructure Maintenance and Projects Department (IMPD) Computer Systems and Network Administrator	* System Maintainers
Informing residents about the possibility of applying for notification	Ensure the largest possible contact list of residents so that notification in case of threat is productive	The number of residents who have applied for notification has increased	* MOIC Contact Centre Data Operator	* Resident

Stages of the process of notifying the CP Commission of the CP Commission convocation/CP event and maintaining and updating the list of CP Commission members:

Figure 5. **CP Commission Notification**

Notifying or warning residents in case of a potential threat, maintaining and testing the notification system, training employees to use the tool, and informing residents about the opportunity to apply for notification - process steps:

Figure 6. **Notification of the residents**

The specificity of Jelgava MOIC is that the core business processes of MOIC also include CP processes. Early warning is part of CP and the created early warning functionality can be used to notify residents not only in the event of floods, but also in all other cases when it is necessary to convey uniform and operational information to residents of a certain geographical area.

3. Resources required to ensure full-fledged operation of MOIC

3.1. Necessary resources for the operation of MOIC

The resources necessary to ensure the operation of MOIC can be conditionally divided into the following groups:

- financing;
- human resources;
- premises;
- equipment;
- technology;
- documentation;
- collaboration partners.

Financing

In the case of Jelgava, MOIC financing is mainly from the municipal budget; individual projects are implemented with European Union project funds. Of all the expenditure segments, the largest is remuneration of employees – around 65% of all expenses, the rest is payment for services, social payments and compensations, capital expenditures and expenses for the purchase of materials and energy resources. In each individual case, it is possible to secure financing from other sources, for example, by operating as a company and providing services to local governments.

Human Resources

To ensure the operation of MOIC, taking the Jelgava MOIC as an example in terms of both geographical area and population, as well as cooperation partners and the processes they're involved in, and based on the current workload of MOIC services, 9 full-time positions are required, including the Head of MOIC and CP Engineer. A detailed description of the positions, responsibilities and required competencies of employees is described in section 3.2 of the Handbook.

Premises

Taking into account the specifics of MOIC operations, the premises in which the MOIC is located do not have to be in the very centre of the city/populated area. However, taking into account involvement in CP actions, the location of the MOIC at a relatively short distance from the most important objects of the city may be preferred in some cases. The premises in which it is intended to ensure the operation of the MOIC must be so spacious that at least 5 employees can work comfortably at the same time. Considering that the service must be provided 24x7, a rest room must be provided in which the minimum necessary equipment would be located, in cases where Data Operators need to record information provided by residents or Cooperation Partners.

If the MOIC is established as a structural unit of another institution, the premises must be as spacious as necessary to ensure the operation of the rest of the institution. If the MOIC is planned to be combined in the same premises with another service provider or operational service or part thereof (similarly, as is the case in Jelgava - the Municipal Police Department, which performs the analysis of city video observations, is also located in the same premises with the MOIC), it is necessary to provide space for this service provider/operational service as well. When thinking about the layout of the premises, it is important to foresee whether cooperation with this service provider/operational service may potentially be necessary.

Equipment

At least 5 computerized workplaces with ergonomic office furniture and computer equipment are required to ensure the operation of the MOIC, providing for 5 full-time positions (Head of MOIC, Head of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Department, Fire Safety and Civil Protection Engineer (CP Specialist), MOIC Contact Centre Head and Contact Centre Data Operator). In addition to the standard computer equipment set, the Data Operator's workplace must be provided with additional monitors for monitoring the city's infrastructure. An additional computerized workplace in the recreation room is required to ensure night rest.

The Data Operator must also be provided with a handheld transceiver and a work phone, the number of which is connected to WhatsApp, as well as equipment for ensuring handheld transceiver recording. In cases where a large call flow is expected, it is necessary to consider purchasing a hands-free system for Data Operators, thus freeing their hands for immediate operations in the systems.

Technologies

The following technologies/systems are used to ensure the operation of MOIC:

- application processing solution JVIAS, within which both MOIC Data Operators and MOIC cooperation partners can work, or with the cooperation partner system PUKS (pilsetsaim-nieciba.lv) integrated application processing system JVIAS;
- telephony solution Cisco Finesse (web version), which is integrated with the application processing system with call recording and forwarding function - services must be integrated with the application processing system;
- SMS sending module WEB version (CSC Telecom);
- call blocking system (bpos);
- map for applications (Interactive map, mobile application);
- business intelligence solution MS Power BI (Qlik business intelligence solution in the implementation stage) for obtaining and analyzing JUICS statistical data;
- access to monitoring solutions - for example, ImFlow and Peek Traffic (traffic light systems), LUFT (weather stations), Alnet CMS (video surveillance), ABB Scada (rainwater pumping stations and flood gates), City light (<https://citylight.teliko.com:3000/>), Geopolitical Information System (GIS), energo.jelgava.lv/Ellat SCADA, generator monitoring system;
- map <http://10.10.10.108/gmsc/?sso=true> and GeoMedia Smart Client for marking early warning polygons and transferring information to JVIAS;
- GPS system (navirec.com);
- LED billboard information solution (RGB Colour studio and others);
- population map system ([Visvaris](http://visvaris.lv));
- SLS data publishing portal (kadastrs.lv);
- JUICS system operation problem reporting module (mantis.meditec.lv);
- radio communication.

In cases where the MOIC's activities are planned to be expanded or the relevant municipality has some specifics that impose additional obligations on the MOIC or about which the MOIC must be informed, it may be necessary to equip the MOIC with additional monitoring solutions, systems or other technologies.

Documentation

The specifics of MOIC operations involve working with a large and diverse amount of information, which is specific to each topic and cooperation partner.

It is recommended to divide all documents that will become an integral part of MOIC's daily work into groups, for example, as indicated in the Summary by Processes of the manual (Figure 4). It is important to ensure that employees have access to up-to-date process maps for main and support processes, as well as instructions for IT solutions and other systems. If MOIC is created as an independent institution (and not as part of another institution), it is necessary to provide standardized documentation for such support processes as personnel, data protection, procurement, legal and financial processes.

It is important to initially determine the persons responsible for updating documents and determine the regularity of document reviews. In order to ensure clear, unambiguous and accurate execution of actions by Data Operators, the availability of standardized and up-to-date information in one place becomes vital for the speed of application processing.

Cooperation partners

The main function of MOIC is to ensure coordinated information flow between residents and various cooperation partners. The minimum range of cooperation partners with whom cooperation must be agreed in any municipality includes operational services and partners that ensure the maintenance of the city or municipality territory. Detailed information on possible cooperation arrangements is described in section 5 of the Handbook.

3.2. MOIC structure, job descriptions and job functions

MOIC is part of the Jelgava Digital Centre and is visible in the structure as a separate JDC structural unit (see Figure 7 below).

Figure 7. *JDC structure*

The Head of MOIC is subordinate to the Head of the Jelgava Digital Centre. The MOIC structural unit includes the Head of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Department, a Fire Safety and Civil Protection Engineer, a Head of Contact Centre and five Data Operators. According to the JDC staff list, 9 employees work at MOIC. The Head of MOIC also performs the duties of the Head deputy of JDC if necessary. MOIC operations are ensured 24 hours a day throughout the calendar year.

Table 2. *MOIC positions*

Job Title	Working Hours	Number of Employees
Head of MOIC	Normal Working Hours	1
Head of Fire Safety and Civil Protection Department	Normal Working Hours	1
Fire Safety and Civil Protection Engineer	Normal Working Hours	1
Head of MOIC Contact Centre	Normal Working Hours	1
Contact Centre Data Operator	Aggregate Working Hours with 24-Hour Shift	5

The tables below summarize the job objectives, required education, required skills, and direct duties and tasks for each position.

Table 3. *Job description: Head of MOIC*

Job objective	To organize, plan and coordinate the work of the structural unit, including organizing coordinated information flow between the Institution and residents, state and local government institutions, enterprises, operational entities and owners or legal holders of critical infrastructure, as well as its analysis, planning and organizing the development of the local government civil protection system, monitoring and managing critical infrastructure monitoring systems, storing, processing and analyzing data provided by critical infrastructure maintainers or legal holders.
Required education	Academic higher education or second-level professional higher education supplemented with appropriate specialized courses. Periodic updating of knowledge in courses and seminars in the required field
Required skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Good communication and interpersonal skills Foreign language skills Good computer skills Independent work organization National language skills at the highest level (C2) Team management skill

Direct duties and tasks

- ensure the functional and administrative work of the structural unit of the Institution and subordinate employees;
- ensure the registration of information received in the structural unit, transfer to the local government Cooperation Partners for further action, collect and analyze information about the actions of the Cooperation Partners (work execution schedules, actual work performance, situation resolution, etc.);
- organize measures to improve the quality and efficiency of the structural unit's work as necessary;
- identify the set of local-scale critical infrastructure and ensure the supervision and management of critical infrastructure monitoring systems, storage, processing and analysis of data provided by critical infrastructure maintainers or legal holders;
- organize and ensure the fulfillment of the functions and tasks of the commission in accordance with the regulations of the civil protection commission of the cooperation territory (hereinafter - the Commission);
- conduct an analysis of municipal-scale accidents and extraordinary events and provide information to the Commission, state and local government institutions, residents, enterprises, operational activity subjects and owners or legal holders of critical infrastructure;
- organize publicity and public relations activities related to accidents and emergency events;
- coordinate the attraction of civil protection and disaster management resources and their actual delivery at the required place, time and quantity;
- perform risk management (including risk identification, assessment, determination and implementation of risk mitigation and control measures) within the framework of their official duties and within the framework of established processes and/or procedures, as well as report to the Head of the Institution on the identification of a new risk that affects or may adversely affect the performance of duties or the fulfillment of the Institution's goals and functions;
- participate in the development of the Institution's current budget and work plan and in the preparation of changes to the plan;
- plan and organize the provision of the structural unit's operations;
- monitor the actual quantity of the structural unit's materials and inventory and ensure their use planning and delivery;
- plan and organize the procurement necessary for the needs of the structural units;
- ensure the development and implementation of development planning documents, as well as participate in the development of the Institution's project applications and the implementation of approved projects;
- prepare draft council decisions, if necessary to ensure the work of the structural unit;
- participate in the development and conclusion of draft cooperation agreements;
- within the scope of their competence, participate in the work of working groups, meetings, commissions, develop draft information reports and represent the structural unit within the scope of its competence in international working groups;
- perform other tasks determined by the Head of the Institution in accordance with the competence of the structural unit.

Table 4. *Job description: Head of the Fire Safety and Civil Protection Department of MOIC*

Job objective	Ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution and other institutions/residents; ensure operational information preparation, information flow and data analysis. Perform all necessary civil protection, fire safety and occupational safety duties, as well as implement appropriate actions in the event of disasters and disaster threats
Required education	Higher or second-level professional higher education. Preferred training, professional development certificate in labor protection (60-hour program completed)
Required skills	<p>Good communication and interpersonal skills Ability to work in high-intensity conditions Presentation preparation (including instruction) skills Organize, plan and coordinate the work of the Department Knowledge of the legal aspects of the civil protection system and the organization of the system Practical work experience</p>
Direct duties and tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● perform duties in accordance with the procedures established by the Institution and the orders of the direct manager or the head of the Institution; ● organize, plan and coordinate the work of the department, ensure the operational preparation of information: perform quality control of the performance of duties and tasks of the department employees; monitor the operation of the necessary processes that ensure the quality of services; ● perform all necessary work duties in the field of CP - participate in the development of the CP plan, constantly update the CP plan, inform, train employees on civil protection issues, participate in the work of the Commission, advise heads of institutions and the management of the municipality; ● control the assessment of work environment risks and fire safety risks and the prediction and monitoring of possible consequences, as well as, within the scope of the competence of the position, carry out the assessment of civil protection risks and the prediction of possible consequences upon the instructions of the direct manager; ● prepare internal regulations (instructions, procedures and other documents) in accordance with the requirements set out in regulatory enactments in the field of fire safety and civil protection; ● plan civil protection measures, cooperate with the joint Commission of the cooperation territory; ● participate in the work of working groups, meetings, committees, and develop draft information reports.

Table 5. *Job description: Fire and Civil Protection Engineer of MOIC*

<p>Job objective</p>	<p>To ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution and the population; to ensure the preparation of documents and data related to civil protection, the collection of necessary information from municipal institutions and Jelgava City municipal enterprises, information flow and data analysis. To perform all necessary duties in the field of civil protection, fire safety and occupational safety</p>
<p>Required education</p>	<p>Higher or second-level professional higher education. Preferred training, professional development certificate in labor protection (60-hour program completed)</p>
<p>Required skills</p>	<p>Good communication and interpersonal skills Ability to work in high-intensity conditions Presentation preparation (including instruction) skills Knowledge of the legal aspects of the civil protection system and the organization of the system Ability to prepare draft documents and documents in the field of civil protection and fire safety Practical work experience Independent organization of work</p>
<p>Direct duties and tasks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● perform duties in accordance with the procedures established by the Institution and the orders of the direct manager or head of the Institution; ● perform all necessary work duties in the field of CP - participate in the development of the CP plan, constantly update the CP plan, inform, train employees on civil protection issues, participate in the work of the Commission, advise heads of institutions and local government management; ● perform work environment risk and fire safety risk assessment and possible consequences forecasting and monitoring, as well as within the scope of the position, upon the instructions of the direct manager; perform civil protection risk assessment and possible consequences forecasting; ● prepare internal regulations (instructions, procedures and other documents) in accordance with the requirements set out in regulatory enactments in the field of fire safety and civil protection; plan civil protection measures, cooperate with the joint Commission of the cooperation territory; ● participate in the work of working groups, meetings, commissions, develop draft information reports; ● participate in the organization of briefings and practical training in fire safety; ● control the maintenance of fire extinguishing equipment and fire protection systems, organize their regular inspections and maintenance, plan renovation and improvement works of fire protection systems; ● organize and plan work related to internal monitoring of the working environment, risk assessment and measures to prevent or reduce them; ● develop and maintain the company's internal regulatory base in the field of labor protection;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● systematically inspect the company’s working environment and determine its impact on the surrounding environment, identify and assess work environment risks; ● organize mandatory health checks for employees in accordance with applicable regulatory enactments; ● maintain and update electronic databases and registers in the Institution; ● request information from municipal institutions and Jelgava enterprises within the framework of the performance of other specified duties.
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Table 6. *Job description: Head of MOIC Contact Centre*

Job objective	To organize, plan and coordinate the work of the department in order to ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution and the population, state and local government institutions, enterprises, operational entities and owners or legal holders of critical infrastructure, as well as its analysis. To ensure planning of the department’s priorities, tasks and activities and the establishment of a system for controlling their implementation
Required education	Higher education
Required skills	Analytical thinking, ability to solve problems and make decisions Good cooperation and communication skills Accuracy and high sense of responsibility
Direct duties and task	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● perform duties in accordance with procedures established by the Institution and orders of the direct or head of the Institution; ● organize, plan and coordinate the work of the department, ensure operational information preparation, information circulation and data analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to carry out quality control of the performance of duties and tasks of the department’s employees; ● to monitor the operation of the necessary processes that ensure the quality of services; ● to ensure the continuous operation of the contact centre; ● to maintain and analyze information in the Institution’s existing electronic databases; ● to provide consultations to residents and institutions; ● to prepare information for state, local government institutions, and mass media at the request of the manager. ● to replace an absent employee within their competence in accordance with the order of the Head of the Institution; ● to prepare internal regulatory documents within their competence; ● to participate in the work of working groups, meetings, commissions, to develop draft information reports.

Table 7. *Job description: Contact Centre Data Operator*

Job objective	Accept and register applications from residents, provide information about them and transfer information about the execution of the application to the responsible authority or institution; accept and register information submitted by cooperation partners; ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution, residents and cooperation partners; ensure operational information preparation and data analysis
Required education	Higher education or incomplete higher, secondary or second-level vocational education
Required skills	<p>Clear, structured and professional communication Detailed understanding of the service to be provided and the actions to be performed Excellent computer skills, fast typing skills Tolerance towards different personality types Empathy Problem solving skills Listening skills Ability to organize one's work Foreign language skills High accuracy and sense of responsibility Ability to work in high-intensity conditions</p>
Direct duties and task	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● perform duties in accordance with the procedures established by the Institution, the orders of the Head of Contact Centre or the Head of the MOIC; ● accept applications from reporters, provide information about them and transfer information about the execution of the application to the responsible institution, ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution and residents, structural units of the Jelgava City Municipality and capital companies in which the Jelgava City Council is a shareholder, subjects of operational activities and owners or legal possessors of critical infrastructure - for the successful performance of their direct work tasks, recording the information processing process in the Institution's information systems; ● perform operational control of the Institution and the information systems under the supervision of the Institution and coordinate the flow of the obtained information in accordance with the Institution's procedures; ● ensure operational preparation of information and data analysis of the information registered in the Institution's information systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● within the scope of competence, perform video surveillance (traffic flows, city infrastructure, civil protection); ● perform voice radio communication and send text messages to a mobile phone (mobile phone SMS text message module) to certain notification groups; ● perform coordinated information exchange on disasters, disaster threats, crisis situations, CP training, recording the information processing process in the Institution's information systems;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● collect and provide answers to residents' questions and suggestions within the scope of its competence (or transfer information to structural units of the Jelgava City Municipality and capital companies in which the Jelgava City Council is a shareholder, to subjects of operational activities and owners or legal possessors of critical infrastructure) on the interactive map: www.karte.jelgava.lv; ● upon request, perform early notification of residents (mobile phone SMS text message module or other solution); ● in accordance with the regulations of the Civil Protection Commission of the cooperation territory, ensure notification of the persons in the composition of the Civil Protection Commission of the cooperation territory and invited persons about the convening of the commission meeting; ● ensure operational preparation of information, information circulation and data analysis for the work needs of the Civil Protection Commission of the cooperation territory; ● prepare reports on shift work (including statistical reports on registered reports).
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The necessary skills and personality traits of Data Operators are determined based on the content and objectives of the service to be provided by MOIC. In this context, it is important that:

- communication is ensured with both residents and Cooperation Partners;
- all communication is recorded and forwarded in Information Technology (IT) systems;
- resident does not always understand that the Data Operator is not a person who physically ensures the resolution of the reported problems or who can directly influence the speed of the reported problem and therefore is not always correct when reporting a problem.

Data Operators' Work Quality Assessment Process

A negotiation assessment commission has been established to assess the quality of data operators' work. The negotiation assessment criteria are divided into two blocks:

- one section determines and assesses the employee's communication skills and skills to navigate the services provided by MOIC;
- the second section assesses the quality of the technical design of the employee's report.

Both aspects are assessed on a 10-point system, with 10 points as the maximum rating. The second block has a coefficient of 0.7, thus placing greater emphasis on the employee's communication skills and knowledge than on the quality of the technical design of the report.

The customer service standard describes in detail the distribution of points to be awarded within the framework of the assessment, reducing the possibility of subjectively assessing negotiations. Additional vacation days are provided, and employees are provided with feedback on necessary improvements.

Considering that the employee assessment process is a sensitive activity, no matter how objective the assessment is, it is necessary to ensure that the assessee is interested in receiving feedback and work on improvements together with their immediate supervisor. It would also be advisable to pay attention to the composition of the assessment committee - the motivation of employees to improve performance on the basis of the feedback received directly correlates with the extent to which the assessor is an example and inspires respect for the examinee.

3.3. Data Operator resource capacity

The largest MOIC human resource is engaged in servicing reports from residents and cooperation partners - accepting reports, providing information, transferring information to the institution or body responsible for the execution of the application, ensuring coordinated information flow between the Institution and residents, the Jelgava City Council, municipal institutions and capital companies, operational entities and owners or legal holders of critical infrastructure, and recording information processing processes in the Institution's information systems.

Workforce capacity assessment is a process that allows you to assess whether a structural unit has enough employees to provide a service for the current and future workload. As part of the capacity assessment, the following values are mathematically calculated:

- what is the amount of resources allocated to the work;
- what service availability needs to be ensured;
- what is the actual workload of active employees.

Hours required to ensure service availability

The service described must be provided 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. Thus, the service must be available 8,760 hours a year. During the day, the Data Operator has a basic workplace with all monitors available, but during the night, the Data Operator has access to a rest room with equipment for handling calls and a computer for creating night reports or activities.

Sufficiency of resources involved to ensure service availability

The optimal ratio between how many resources (in available working hours) are involved in providing the service and how many working hours are required to provide the service ranges from 105% to 110%. If this ratio is lower, then as the absence time increases and exceeds the planned, a shortage of resources may occur and, accordingly, the inability to provide the service with the resources involved in the work. In this case, overtime work will occur for existing employees or there will be a need to attract additional resources from other structural units. If this ratio is higher, it is not possible to ensure full-time work for the resources involved.

Actual active resource utilization and resource utilization rate

Actual active employee utilization is the time in hours spent performing active activities to provide a service. This rate does not include downtime. To calculate this factor, the provision of a service is divided into countable and time-measurable activities, determining the average time required to perform each activity and the number of activities performed. Next, the number of each type of activity is multiplied by the time required to perform this activity. By summing the results of all individual activities, the total time spent by employees performing active activities to provide a service is determined.

Using these calculations and the calculation of the hours required to ensure the availability of the service, the resource utilization rate is calculated. The resource utilization rate allows you to determine how much of the working time employees spend performing active activities within the framework of the fulfillment of their assigned duties.

To determine the resource utilization rate, this total time is divided by the hours required to ensure the availability of the service. The resource utilization rate in standard situations is considered optimal when it falls within the range of 75% to 85%. If this rate (calculated monthly) fluctuates below 75% - the employee workload is considered insufficient. If the rate (calculated

monthly) exceeds 85%, then the employee workload is assessed as very high. As a result of very high workload, the quality provision of the service becomes challenging and the risk of employee burnout also increases. An insufficient workload rate reveals the potential for increasing the volume of services using existing resources, or creates the need to review the amount of resources involved.

When evaluating the resource utilization indicator readings in the context of MOIC, it should be noted that the service is provided according to the 24x7 model. The utilization of services provided at night is almost always significantly lower than during the day. Therefore, in the case of MOIC, the optimal indicator level can also be determined within 45-50%.

Despite the lower optimal indicator that can be applied in the case of MOIC, when replicating MOIC operations, there is a possibility to restructure the service provision model:

1. significantly increasing the volumes of service provision;
2. significantly reducing the hours of service availability;
3. using a combined solution - moderately increasing the volumes of service provision and moderately reducing the hours of service availability.

The idea behind MOIC is to provide 24x7 support, and this is exactly how MOIC works - each data operator works a 24-hour shift. Such a work regime may prove unacceptable or very burdensome for potential employees, therefore, when replicating MOIC, an appropriate work schedule should be chosen - 24x7 or 12x2x7. When choosing the second type of work schedule, there is a possibility of providing work in the evening and night hours while the employee is remotely, for example, at home. In the case of incoming applications, the employee can immediately record the received information in the appropriate systems, if the employee is provided with remote access to them.

4. MOIC regulatory framework

MOIC is a structural unit of the Jelgava City Municipal Institution JDC. The activities of MOIC are determined in the JDC regulations, from which it follows that the functions applicable to the activities of MOIC are as follows:

- to ensure coordinated information flow between the Institution and residents, state and municipal institutions, enterprises, operational entities and owners or legal holders of critical infrastructure, as well as its analysis;
- to ensure the maintenance and development of the municipal civil protection system, as well as to carry out supervision and management of critical infrastructure monitoring systems, storage, processing and analysis of data provided by critical infrastructure maintainers or legal holders.

In turn, the tasks attributable to the MOIC are as follows:

- to ensure convenient information flow for information providers and recipients regarding communal services, housing stock, improvement of the administrative territory, public order;
- to coordinate information processing, that is, registration of information, transfer to the local government cooperation partners for further action, obtaining information about the actions of the cooperation partners (work execution schedules, actual work execution, situation resolution, etc.), provision of information to the person requesting it;
- to conduct an analysis of emergency events, develop prevention measures and prepare reports for the Jelgava Cooperation Territory Civil Protection Commission;
- to collect and provide the necessary information to the Commission, state and local government institutions, residents, enterprises, operational entities and owners or legal possessors of critical infrastructure in emergency situations;

- to coordinate local government civil protection and disaster management measures;
- to participate in state civil protection and disaster management measures;
- to carry out early identification of risks of disasters, accidents and injuries and to involve the population in measures to prevent these risks;
- to compile and analyze information available to the JDC.

Given that MOIC is part of JDC, some of the regulatory acts that are binding on JDC as a municipal institution may not be directly applicable to MOIC's core business processes. However, it is not possible to separate which external regulatory acts would be binding only on JDC and which would not be directly applicable to MOIC, given that MOIC is an integral part of JDC.

External regulatory enactments that directly or indirectly regulate the activities of MOIC:

- Local Government Law;
- State Information Systems Law;
- Electronic Documents Law;
- Civil Protection and Disaster Management Law;
- Information Transparency Law;
- Law on Submissions;
- Personal Data Processing Law;
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation);
- Law on the Remuneration of Officials and Employees of State and Local Government Institutions;
- Binding Regulations of the Jelgava City Municipality;
- Jelgava Digital Centre Statute.

5. Cooperation with Municipal partners within the framework of MOIC activities

MOIC has several Cooperation Partners - mostly Jelgava city municipal institutions and capital companies, as well as operational services. These partners are often managing sensor networks providing actual data to them and MOIC.

Cooperation agreements have been concluded with individual partners. The efficiency and productivity of cooperation, as well as the resolution of issues that have arisen between MOIC and Cooperation Partners, can be assessed differently. Information on the largest Cooperation Partners is summarized below in Table 8. The table does not include data on those Cooperation Partners whose application share is below 1%, according to available statistics. It should be noted that the submitted statistics for calculating the application share of Cooperation Partners are not sufficiently accurate, as they contain positions that are not considered "Cooperation Partners", for example, the position "Information Exchange". Consequently, the actual application share for each partner is higher than indicated in the table.

Table 8. *Summary of information describing cooperation partners*

Cooperation Partner	Application rate	Contract existence	Partner IT solution
JCMI ¹ "Pilsētsaimniecība" (plans, organizes and controls the infrastructure and improvement of the city's administrative territory)	33%	None. Partner prepares and submits MOIC instruction.	PUKS
<p>Comments: The instruction contains information on the types of problems, the responsible specialists of the Cooperation Partner, the deadline for work completion and the information transfer channels.</p> <p>MOIC Data Operators evaluate the cooperation well, however, it would be necessary to review the performance of certain activities on the part of MOIC Data Operators, which duplicate what the employees of the JCMI "Pilsētsaimniecība" do, for example, in case of problems with pumping stations, MOIC Data Operators must report to the responsible employee, but the responsible employees themselves also see information about these problems online. This reporting is not useful. There are cases when the responsible person is away and separately asks the Data Operator to inform if changes are observed in the monitors.</p>			
Jelgava City Municipality Capital Company Ltd. "Zemgales EKO" (waste management)	9%	A Cooperation Agreement on data exchange via JUICS has been concluded	JUICS
<p>Comments: The contract stipulates the time for acceptance or rejection of the application by the Cooperation Partner. In addition, the signed annex also stipulates the time for application execution and execution control. The JVIAS application processing instructions are attached to the contract.</p> <p>MOIC Data Operators rate the cooperation well.</p>			
JMCI "Jelgava Municipal Police"	7%	It is planned to conclude a contract	MOIC processes the activities in the system JUICS instead of the collaboration partner.
<p>Comments: MOIC also welcomes cases when the Cooperation Partner informs MOIC about significant events on its own initiative.</p> <p>MOIC Data Operators evaluate the cooperation well.</p>			
Jelgava City Municipality (about resident and student cards)	7%	None	None
<p>Comments: MOIC Data Operators rate the cooperation well.</p>			
State Fire and Rescue Service	4%	None	None
<p>Comments: MOIC Data Operators rate the cooperation well.</p>			
Jelgava Real Estate Department (JREB)	Under 3%	The contract is concluded	JUICS, but it is not used
<p>Comments: The contract stipulates a time for acceptance or rejection of the application by the Cooperation Partner. The time for execution of the application and control of execution are not stipulated. The contract does not include instructions for processing JUICS applications.</p>			

¹ JCMI - Jelgava City Municipality Institution

Contracts concluded and agreements settled with Cooperation Partners

When evaluating the contracts concluded between MOIC and Ltd. “Zemgales Eko”, as well as between MOIC and JREB, it is possible to conclude that the text of the Framework Agreement is standardized and stipulates:

- The Cooperation Partner’s access to the system, the procedure for requesting and removing access;
- MOIC’s responsibility for granting access, system maintenance and updates;
- the time within which the Cooperation Partner must accept or reject the task specified in the application;
- other rights and obligations.

No written contract has been concluded with MOIC’s largest Cooperation Partner - JCMI “Pilsēt-saimniecība” - but there is a mutual agreement on the exchange of information, in accordance with the document “Instructions on the operational competence of JCMI “Pilsēt-saimniecība” in daily work”, which is regularly updated. This document stipulates in detail the channels for transferring information expected from MOIC and the deadlines for completing applications from JCMI “Pilsēt-saimniecība”.

When assessing the productivity of cooperation and the parties’ adherence to the established procedure and deadlines for processing applications, and their relationship with the obligations stipulated in the Agreements and their annexes, a clear trend is clearly visible that the detailed provision of response time and control over the execution of applications in the agreement is directly related to successful and productive cooperation. However, it should be recognized that in the case of a large number of applications, a model also works well in which, in addition to a formalized agreement between the parties, there is a clear Instruction that reflects the areas of responsibility and contact persons of the Cooperation Partner, stipulates the channels for transferring information and deadlines for resolving applications. This model can work as long as both parties adhere to their mutual agreements.

Systems used for processing applications

Currently, two Cooperation Partners (who are the Executors of applications registered in MOIC) transfer information about the execution of the application to MOIC using JVIAS or the PUKS solution integrated with JUICS. In this case, Cooperation Partners can see the received applications, add comments and see the comments added by MOIC workers, accept or reject applications, and mark the status of the application’s forwarding.

If the Cooperation Partner does not have access to the system, then the Application statuses are changed by the MOIC Data Operator based on the information received from the Cooperation Partner. This requires additional time on the Data Operator’s side. These actions allow collecting statistics on applications and ensuring control over the execution of applications.

Contact information of cooperation partners for residents

The distribution of applications by cooperation partners shows that the largest cooperation partner of MOIC in terms of the number of applications is for JCMI “Pilsētsaimniecība”. From the available information, it can be concluded that the relatively large number of applications is contributed by the following factors:

1. the broad scope of responsibility of JCMI “Pilsētsaimniecība” - 45 application topics are attributable to this partner;
2. MOIC telephone number 8787 for applications from residents is indicated in the contact section of the JCMI “Pilsētsaimniecība” website.

The areas of other cooperation partners are not so broad, for comparison: 9 application topics are attributable to Ltd. “Zemgales EKO”, and 28 application topics to JREB. None of these partners indicates the MOIC telephone number 8787 for applications from residents related to these topics in the contact section of the website.

Recommended cooperation model between MOIC and Cooperation Partners

When looking at the desired cooperation model, it is important to take into account the diversity of MOIC Cooperation Partners. MOIC has Cooperation Partners to whom MOIC transfers information received from residents in the form of work assignments. In this case, the Cooperation Partner is responsible for evaluating, accepting or rejecting this assignment, executing it and transferring the relevant information to MOIC. In turn, MOIC is responsible for accepting the application, transferring accurate information to the Cooperation Partner, informing the resident about the time of resolving the application, tracking the execution through the information provided by the Cooperation Partner. Such partners are, for example, JCMI “Pilsētsaimniecība”, Ltd. “Zemgales EKO”, JREB.

There are also Cooperation Partners that provide information necessary for MOIC’s work or give tasks to MOIC. In these cases, the Cooperation Partner is responsible for transferring accurate and sufficiently detailed information to MOIC. In turn, MOIC is responsible for accurately recording information for its work, transferring information to residents, and executing the task. Such partners are, for example, State Fire and Rescue Service, JSC “Sadales tīkls” (Electricity Network Operator and Developer).

Individual Cooperation Partners can fulfill both of the indicated roles. Such Cooperation Partners are, for example, JCMI “Pilsētsaimniecība”, Jelgava City Municipality in relation to Resident Cards or the Municipal Police.

Thus, Cooperation Partners can be conditionally divided into the following groups:

- Executors;
- Information Providers and/or Task Givers;
- Partners that fulfill both of the above-mentioned roles.

The cooperation model must take into account the diversity of Cooperation Partners. Requirements for the legal form of cooperation, the use of IT systems for receiving or transferring information and tasks and marking the progress of implementation, as well as requirements for indicating MOIC contact information on the websites of Cooperation Partners, must be standardized, based on the purpose of cooperation and the Cooperation Partner’s affiliation to the relevant groups.

Cooperation model with Cooperation Partners belonging to the Group of Executors

To set down the terms of cooperation, obligations and responsibilities with this group of Cooperation Partners, it would be advisable to conclude standardized contracts, which would stipulate all the necessary cooperation requirements. Only the conclusion of a contract imposes binding obligations on both parties and allows the parties to structure legal aspects such as:

- access to the JUICS system and MOIC's actions in cases where inappropriate or malicious actions are performed in the system;
- detailed information on the topics of applications, responsible persons, deadlines for accepting and resolving applications;
- personal data protection;
- data quality requirements and the data quality verification process;
- and others.

When working with existing Cooperation Partners who are Executors of applications registered in MOIC, it is advisable to reach an agreement between the parties on working in JUICS or with the JUICS integrated system, saving time resources for both parties, since transferring information by e-mail or by telephone takes more time for both parties than marking the status of the application in the system.

MOIC should also provide training materials for working with JUICS to relevant employees of all Cooperation Partners included in this group, if the work is not carried out in the integrated system. Process schemes for accepting applications, transferring tasks, recording task status and JUICS instructions are also an essential part of such cooperation.

Taking into account the human resource capacity available at MOIC, it would be advisable to develop cooperation with these Cooperation Partners in such a way that they indicate the MOIC phone number in the contact sections of their websites and thus increase the number of applications processed by MOIC Data Operators.

Cooperation model with Cooperation partners belonging to the Information Provider/Task Giver group

Cooperation with such Cooperation partners imposes obligations on MOIC, but requires only the precise formulation of the information/task from the Information Provider/Task Giver. Accordingly, in these cases, concluding a contract is not proportionate. However, it would be advisable to discuss the cooperation model at the level of heads of institutions or responsible persons and agree on its observance. It is also important to achieve a common understanding of the procedure for providing feedback in cases where the cooperation model is not observed - for example, if information/tasks are transferred using the wrong channel, without observing the agreement on the terms of timely information and in other equivalent cases.

Cooperation model with Cooperation Partners fulfilling both of the above-mentioned roles

Taking into account the specifics of MOIC's work, it is permissible that such cooperation will be developed mainly with local government institutions. If the Cooperation Partner fulfills both of the above-mentioned roles and a contract is concluded with this Cooperation Partner as the Executor, it would be advisable to add a separate standardized section to this contract, which would stipulate the procedure for transferring information/tasks.

The agreement should determine the topics of information/tasks (if they can be standardized and known), the deadlines and channel for timely submission of information/tasks, the responsible persons of both parties, and the feedback process in cases where the agreed procedure is not followed.

6. Necessary preparations for replicating MOIC activities in other municipalities

The existence of an operational information centre in a city/municipality/territory can have many benefits. The most important benefits are:

- improvement of environmental safety - fast and coordinated resolution of reported problems is carried out;
- involvement of residents in maintaining the municipality's environment - a convenient and modern single point of contact solution is used, the resident does not have to think about where to turn;
- prompt information to municipal leaders about significant events that may have a potential negative impact.

In order to ensure the replication of the Jelgava MOIC model in other places, recommendations have been prepared below, structured in three parts:

- actions to be taken before replicating the MOIC model in other territories;
- recommendations for a common MOIC replication strategy;
- decisions to be made in the relevant municipality before a MOIC is created there.

6.1. Steps to be taken before replicating the MOIC model in other territories

To ensure high-quality replication of the Jelgava MOIC in another territory, it is necessary to carry out preparatory work:

- creation of a unified manual on the actions of the Data Operator in various cases, depending on the topic of the application;
- creation of an intranet page for the manual and other materials important for work;
- creation of the desired cooperation model with operational services and various Cooperation Partners;
- increasing the popularity of the notification tool to ensure maximum contact coverage of residents;
- implementation, standardization or updating of documents that determine the operation of the centre.

It is recommended to identify the range of services to be provided, as well as the circle of Cooperation Partners to whom the future MOIC will provide support. In order to ensure targeted attraction of Cooperation Partners, it would be necessary to create a role or position of Cooperation Partner Manager in the MOIC structure. Such determination of one responsible employee would also mean a clear development trajectory for the development of MOIC. Perhaps, entrusting such position duties to one of the existing Data Operators could partially optimize the available MOIC resources and ensure the necessary development of MOIC. It would also be necessary to evaluate the possibility of concluding commercial agreements with potential Cooperation Partners, so MOIC would receive payment for the call centre functions provided for processing residents' applications.

6.2. Recommendations for a common MOIC replication strategy

Considering that in many countries the territory is divided into several local government units, when implementing the MOIC concept at the national level, it is essential to develop a unified concept of MOIC responsibilities and core business processes.

A unified MOIC concept should cover:

- management model;
- objectives and responsibilities;
- decision-making powers;

- cooperation models with Cooperation Partners;
- communication standards and channels for information flow with residents and Cooperation Partners;
- IT solutions to be used, including monitoring solutions;
- the potential impact of innovative technologies on the services provided by MOIC;
- social marketing approach.

Adherence to a unified and centralized management model of replicated MOICs would ensure a unified direction and speed of MOIC development, as well as a higher degree of standardization in MOIC processes, documents and IT solutions.

The centralized management model could be implemented by creating a single coordinating institution at the national level, to which all MOIC structures established in regions or municipalities would be subordinate. Taking into account the close connection of MOICs with the relevant municipality, a matrix management model should be evaluated, when the MOIC in each municipality would be functionally subordinate to the relevant municipality, but administrative responsibility would be entrusted to the central coordination institution.

A standardized MOIC concept and unified management would facilitate coordination in the event of national crises, since the activities in which MOIC should be involved and in which MOIC plays a significant role would be centralized. Of course, when creating a unified concept, the specifics of each local government territory should also be taken into account - for example, territories with a high risk of flooding, etc. In these local governments, MOICs may have additional responsibilities and powers that are assigned to them.

One of the main responsibilities of MOIC is accepting applications from residents regarding problems identified in the local government territory and transferring information to responsible persons in the relevant institutions. Thanks to the MOIC's activities, responsible persons receive timely information about the necessary actions to restore environmental safety, thus preventing or mitigating the possible consequences of events and saving financial resources that would be needed to repair major damage. Maintaining a conceptually unified approach between local governments would ensure an understandable MOIC operating model also for those residents who move to different local governments during their lives. If, while living in one municipality, a resident is already informed about the MOIC operating model, when moving to another municipality, they would maintain common habits on how to take care of the environment in their municipality and inform about the identified shortcomings.

Within the framework of the unified concept, when planning the replication of MOIC and the possible development of the MOIC model, it is important to take into account the possible impact of innovative technologies on the resources necessary for the replication and operation of MOIC. Artificial intelligence and other smart solutions can change the service provision model - for example, by allowing the automation of part of the processing of applications without the involvement of Data Operators.

6.3. Decisions that must be made in the relevant municipality before a MOIC is established there

To ensure the full operation of the MOIC in another municipality, it is initially necessary to clearly define the role and planned functions of the MOIC in the relevant municipality. Defining clear roles and functions will facilitate the further operation of the MOIC and help ensure a more fluid exchange of information between the parties involved in the process.

If cooperation with real estate managers and municipal institutions that ensure the maintenance of order in the city is planned:

To ensure optimal cooperation, it would be necessary to agree on the most appropriate cooperation model with each of the managers or other municipal institutions. It would be advisable to adhere to a standardized cooperation model, stipulating that all received information about any damage or issues related to maintaining order in the city is registered in an electronic system, through which applications received by MOIC are delegated to the appropriate institution for further action. The use of such an approach would ensure the efficiency of the process, since the received information would be transferred within a single channel and directly to the responsible institution, as well as the possibility of tracking the registered information and the actions taken would be ensured. It is also advisable to adhere to the conclusion of standardized contracts with these partners, providing a certain section of the contract for the inclusion of special (non-standard) provisions.

If cooperation with operational services is planned:

If cooperation with operational services is planned not within the framework of Civil Protection activities, but in other daily events, it is necessary to discuss the cooperation model between MOIC and other operational services. It is necessary for operational services to include MOIC in their daily action algorithms as one of the participants in the process. It is important that the existing procedure is followed - to ensure this, it is possible to ask for the support of the municipality to strengthen the role of MOIC in the specific municipality, fixing the role of MOIC in writing (in an official order, decision or semi-officially - in an e-mail between the heads of the parties involved or decision-making employees).

The role of MOIC in these processes should be to provide additional support to operational services, not to complicate their work - the involvement model must be consistent with this approach.

If it is planned to provide broader support to the residents of a certain municipality on specific issues:

Municipalities can use MOIC as a tool to provide broader support to the residents of a certain municipality on specific issues. Before directing the residents of a municipality to a specific MOIC, it is important to agree on a cooperation model between the municipality and the MOIC. In cases where the municipality requires the involvement of the MOIC to provide support to the residents, it is important that the municipality informs the MOIC within the specified time interval before the residents are directed to the MOIC to provide the necessary information or receive the necessary information. The municipality or any other institution acting on behalf of the municipality should provide full information to the MOIC management on how to provide support to the residents, coming up with action algorithms. MOIC employees should have clear instructions on how to act when receiving calls from residents. To the extent possible, it should

be ensured that incoming calls can be registered and the received task resolved immediately, or, if such a possibility does not exist, the application should be registered and the information electronically transferred to the responsible authority for further action.

If cooperation with operational services is planned within the framework of Civil Protection activities:

To ensure successful and productive cooperation with operational services within the framework of Civil Protection activities, a clear agreement on the role of the MOIC in this process is necessary. Taking into account the example of the Jelgava MOIC, the municipal MOIC could provide support in attracting the necessary resources, coordinating resources and convening the CP commission and coordinating organizational activities. In this way, the necessary organizational support would be provided, but there would be no interference in the activities of other operational services that are primarily responsible for the implementation/carrying out of CP activities.

After the role of the MOIC in the specified municipality has been defined, it is necessary to define the necessary resources, taking into account the scope of the MOIC's activities. The necessary human resources, infrastructure and other resources are directly related to the defined scope of the MOIC's activities.

The Jelgava MOIC is an example of how municipal operational centres can be organized. By carrying out the necessary preparatory work for the replication of MOICs and later by making a decision to establish MOICs in municipalities, it is possible to significantly improve the quality of life and participation of residents living in municipalities in improving the urban environment.

7. Establishment and operation of Early Warning System

Within the framework of the IMPETUS project, a predictive model of flooded areas was developed for the Zemgale region to ensure timely warning of residents when flood risks increase.

Floods are a natural phenomenon – the overflow of an area when the water level in water bodies rises and the land nearby is flooded. The main causes of floods are prolonged precipitation – intense rain, melting snow and ice, ice jams, storms, tides, man-made disasters – dams, barrages or reservoir collapses.

The territory of the Zemgale planning region is affected by the Lielupe River Basin District and the Daugava River Basin District.

The Lielupe River Basin District (hereinafter - RBD) occupies 8875 km² or 13.7% of the territory of Latvia. The total area of the Lielupe RBD is 17,600 km², approximately half of which is located in the territory of Lithuania. In Lielupe RBD lives about 11.6% of Latvia's population. The largest settlements in the region are Jelgava, Jūrmala, Olaine, Dobeles and Bauska.

Figure 8. *Lielupe River Basin District*

The Lielupe RBD has a prominent hydrographic network and a relatively dense network of small rivers, most of which are potamal-type rivers with a current speed of up to 0.5-1.5 meters per second. The length of the Lielupe is 119 km.

The hydrological regime of rivers and lakes is characterized by high spring floods, summer-autumn rain floods and summer and winter low-water periods. Winter low-water periods are often interrupted by thaws.

The Daugava RBD is located in the eastern and southeastern parts of Latvia. Its area in the territory of Latvia is 27,057 km², which is 42% of the total territory of the country.

Figure 9. *Daugava River Basin District*

The total number of permanent residents of the Daugava RBD is 1.14 million (2019), which is approximately 59% of the total population of Latvia. The largest settlements are Riga, Daugavpils, Rēzekne, Ogre, Mārupe, Jēkabpils, Salaspils, Ķekava and Krāslava.

Flood classification

According to the classification of the Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre (hereinafter - LEGMC), floods can be divided into the following types:

- 🔹 **spring floods;** usually observed in March and April. They are caused by intensive snowmelt, which begins with an increase in air temperature after winter, when a thick layer of snow and ice has accumulated on the ground. Spring floods with rainwater, ice and mudflows can cause local floods or block the flow of rivers. The volume of flood water mainly depends on the volume of snow cover and the increase in the flow rate in rivers. In turn, the maximum water level is determined by the intensity and duration of snowmelt, which is also affected by the filtration properties of the soil - that is, how much melting water can be absorbed into the ground.
- 🔹 **ice jams** form in river sections with reduced longitudinal slope, at river mouths, in places where there are islands, sharp bends, narrowings of the riverbed, as well as in places where water storage in reservoirs ends. Ice and mudflows occur when there is rapid ice movement and large fluctuations in air temperature;
- 🔹 **rain-induced floods** are related to the amount, intensity and distribution area of precipitation, which can cause rapid water level rise and flooding of areas in small rivers. In cities, intense precipitation can cause rapid runoff and exceed the maximum water discharge capacity of rainwater drainage systems. Usually, rain floods occur in the summer and autumn seasons and in some years the maximum flow rate may be higher than the maximum flow rate of spring floods;

- **wind surges** in areas along the sea coast and in the mouths of major rivers - a rise in water level in the sea or in the mouths of rivers, caused by the action of certain winds. Wind surges are usually observed in autumn and early winter, when several active cyclones cross Northern Europe, which cause repeated intensification of westerly winds, contributing to the influx of water into the Baltic Sea and then also into the Gulf of Riga and rivers;
- **anthropogenic floods** are associated with areas where human activity has affected the natural regime of water, thereby exposing previously unthreatened areas to flooding. Floods can occur as a side effect of the construction of reservoirs, polders and other hydraulic structures, as well as as a result of the failure of hydraulic structures (for example, due to internal erosion of a dam). The impact of a failure of hydraulic structures can be amplified by dams at bridges or other river narrowings.

The causes of floods are natural and climatic conditions that determine or contribute to the formation of floods: precipitation intensity, air temperature and humidity, wind direction and speed, terrain, vegetation cover, hydrogeological conditions, hydrographic network and its condition, the size of the catchment area of watercourses and water bodies, morphometric and hydraulic parameters of the river bed.

Flood-prone areas can be divided into two basic groups by origin:

- areas that are flooded as a result of the influence of natural conditions;
- areas that can be flooded as a result of human activity.

7.1. Flood risks

Flood risks refer to the potential hazards arising from flood events and their potential impact on people, property, infrastructure and the environment. Flood risks include both the likelihood of flood events themselves and their consequences.

In Latvia, floods have not been as devastating as in many other European countries, where they have even claimed human lives in recent years. Compared to other European Member States, Latvia has a low population density, extensive construction and land use, as a result of which riverbeds are still in a natural state in many sections. Rivers are characterized by extensive floodplains, preserved wetlands and bogs, which serve as natural flood retention areas.

The Lielupe RBD is one of the most endangered river basins in terms of territorial flooding, due to the flat relief of the basin and the peculiarities of the river hydrographic network. In the Lielupe basin, the threat of flooding exists practically only in the territory of Latvia, because in the territory of Lithuania the river basins are still relatively small and the relief is more pronounced than in the lower reaches of the Lielupe from Bauska to the mouth of the Gulf of Riga.

The economic development of the country also affects the intensity of land use and construction, especially on the coasts of rivers, lakes and the sea. Under the influence of human activity and climate change, the probability of flooding increases, and accordingly the probability of adverse impacts on human health, the environment, cultural heritage and economic activity also increases. The transformation of agricultural land into construction areas, rapid urbanization, long-term unmaintained (overgrown, clogged) surface drainage systems, including in populated areas, are prerequisites for the threat of floods to be observed in places where they did not previously cause problems, because temporary flooding corresponded to the previous type of land use. Climate change also affects the water regime of rivers, the scale of floods and the strength of storms more and more every year.

Floods threaten the environment, the safety of residents, the operation of traffic, communications and electricity supply infrastructure, the availability of medical services, waste management, the operation of industrial facilities, and cause losses to agricultural lands, forests and protected areas. Therefore, identifying areas at risk of flooding and implementing flood management measures is essential not only to protect human lives and the human-made economic environment, but also from the perspective of rational management of natural resources and preservation of environmental diversity.

Flood risks can threaten several aspects and lead to adverse consequences:

- 🔹 **For people:** floods can pose a direct threat to human life and health, especially when floods are sudden. Failure to evacuate and ignoring floods can lead to injuries or deaths.
- 🔹 **For property:** flooding can cause significant damage to buildings, vehicles and other property, which can require long and expensive restoration.
- 🔹 **For infrastructure:** floods can damage roads, bridges, railways, power grids, water supply systems and other critical infrastructure, causing long-term disruption to society.
- 🔹 **For the environment:** floods can cause pollution, as water and wastewater can contain chemicals that negatively affect the quality of ecosystems and drinking water.
- 🔹 **For the economy:** the damage caused by floods can have a significant impact on local and national economies, causing business interruptions, losses in agriculture and tourism, and requiring large resources for restoration work.

To manage flood risks and take preventive action, tools are needed that would allow reducing the consequences of flood risks in case of occurrence. Therefore, an Early Warning System is being developed for the Zemgale Planning Region within the framework of IMPETUS.

The importance of early warning in flood risk management

Early warning is essential to reduce flood damage and increase public safety. Early warning systems allow for timely warning of residents and responsible institutions about impending floods, providing the necessary time for evacuation, property protection and preventive measures.

The early warning process includes:

- 🔗 **Data collection and analysis:** meteorological and hydrometeorological data are used to predict the likelihood and intensity of floods.
- 🔗 **Real-time monitoring:** river level gauges and meteorological stations provide constant monitoring of the situation.
- 🔗 **Warning dissemination:** various communication channels, including SMS, email, mobile applications, social media and traditional media, ensure wide and effective dissemination of warnings.
- 🔗 **Coordination and response plans:** as part of the early warning process, detailed plans are developed that determine the actions of responsible institutions in the event of a flood to ensure an effective and rapid response.

Early warning is critical to mitigating the negative impacts of floods, preserving human life and health, and protecting infrastructure and property.

Given the location of the Jelgava Digital Centre – a territory of the Jelgava City Municipality, which is exposed to flood risk – early notification is an essential tool to ensure prompt information exchange with residents whose properties are located in a potential risk area. The notification process involves multiple parties and affects multiple processes.

7.2. Notification process and involved human resources

Notifying or warning residents in case of potential threat, maintaining and testing the notification system, training employees in the use of the tool and informing residents about the possibility of applying for notification – are the stages of the process.

The core business processes of Jelgava MOIC also include civil protection processes. Early warning is part of CP and the established early warning functionality can be used to notify residents not only in the event of floods, but also in all other cases when it is necessary to provide uniform and operational information to residents of a certain geographical area.

Several persons are involved in the process of notifying residents:

- 🔗 employees who receive information about potential floods,
- 🔗 CP commission, which makes a decision on notification,
- 🔗 an employee who enters the notification process into the system.

In the case of the city of Jelgava, the following are involved in the process:

- 🔗 CP commission of the Jelgava city and Jelgava district cooperation territory;
- 🔗 civil protection specialist who cooperates with the CP commission;
- 🔗 dispatcher who works with the early warning system.

The distribution of roles and processes in which the CP specialist is involved are reflected in Figure 10, which illustrates the workflow of the flood management system, from receiving flood data to preparing an event and sending notifications.

Figure 10. **Event registration scheme**

The aim of the system is to effectively identify areas at risk and to immediately send warnings to responsible persons and residents to ensure timely response and protection against flood threats.

The scheme clearly shows two possible flood data entry paths – automatic entry from the HEC-RAS program and manual entry provided by a CP specialist (information on the HEC-RAS program that models flood risks is summarized in the following section). In both cases, the system performs the same actions to identify affected areas and prepare the necessary notifications. The system provides automatic data processing and determination of flood-affected areas, thereby minimizing the possibility of human error and increasing the speed of response. In both cases, a CP specialist can manually check and supplement the data generated by the system, ensuring accuracy and adaptability to real-world situations.

The workflow starts with one of the options - how the flood hazard data will be entered. As mentioned above, there are two options: use flood models from the HEC-RAS program or let a CP specialist manually mark the area at risk.

If data is entered from the HEC-RAS program, the system processes it, analyzing and providing accurate flood model results. Based on the received data, the system determines the specific addresses and cadastral units that may be affected in the event of a flood risk. The system then prepares an event that includes information about the identified addresses and cadastral units. The workflow ends with the full preparation of the event and the sending of notifications. Once the event is prepared, the system can send a notification to responsible users and residents, informing about the potential flood risk, this process is reflected in Figure 11.

On the other hand, if the CP specialist chooses to manually mark the threatened area, the system then identifies the affected addresses and cadastral units in the same way as with automatic data entry from HEC-RAS. The CP specialist then manually fills in the necessary information about the flood event, based on the identified addresses and cadastral units. After all the information has been entered, the workflow ends with the full preparation of the event and adding the information to the system.

After the event is created, it is notified to the CP commission, which makes a decision – to notify the population or not. The process diagram after the decision is made is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. *Event approval/ rejection scheme*

The workflow begins with the created event, the CP specialist has the opportunity to approve or reject events based on the decision of the CP commission. If the CP specialist approves the event, the workflow continues, moving to the next step, in which the specialist selects the notification type. On the other hand, if the event is rejected, the CA specialist must indicate the reason for the rejection. In this case, the notification is not performed and the workflow ends.

After approving the event, the CP specialist selects whether the notification will be performed manually or automatically. If manual notification is selected, dispatchers perform the notification process and the workflow ends after the notification is completed. If automatic notification is selected, the system automatically sends messages to residents, and the workflow ends when the notification is successfully completed.

The scheme in Figure 11 clearly shows the steps and dependencies of the notification process, emphasizing the central role of the CP specialist in confirming events and choosing the notification method. The system provides two notification methods: manual and automatic, allowing you to adjust the process according to the requirements of the situation. Manual notification provides greater control and accuracy, while automatic notification provides speed and efficiency, especially in emergency situations.

The created workflow provides a clear and structured notification process, which allows the municipality to effectively manage flood risks and ensure timely information transfer to residents. The system offers flexibility, allowing you to choose between manual and automatic notification, thus adapting to different operational scenarios and providing a comprehensive response mechanism.

Early Warning System Maintenance

The employees of the Information Technology Department of the Jelgava Digital Centre, who are responsible for the maintenance of servers and equipment, are also involved in the maintenance and operation of the Early warning system. They perform various tasks to ensure the continuous operation, security and efficiency of the organization's infrastructure, including the operation of the Early warning system:

1. Server management and maintenance - regular server maintenance, data backup, regular updates of server operating systems and applications, etc. activities.
2. Network infrastructure maintenance - incl. hardware maintenance and ensuring network security.
3. Data management and security - Monitoring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
4. User support and training.
5. Maintenance of technical documentation.

These are only the main tasks of the IT department related to the maintenance of IT resources, but depending on the system, the specifics of the institution's operations, and the technologies used - the list of tasks may be even more extensive. The work of the IT department is essential to ensuring that a company's technological infrastructure operates efficiently, securely, and continuously.

8. How to develop an Early warning system?

Before starting the development of an Early warning system, it is important to consider several key factors to ensure its effectiveness and compliance with the objectives. The main aspects to be taken into account are the goals and users of the system, understanding of the legal framework, technical and infrastructure aspects, speed and accuracy of notification, design and content of warning messages, security and resilience to threats, and the ability to adapt and evolve.

It is imperative to determine the main functionality of the system before developing it. It is necessary to understand what the main events will be in which the system will be used (floods, prolonged rainfall or other hazards, such as fires). It is also important to understand who the main users will be - citizens, public authorities, the private sector or specific organizations. It is necessary to define what the sources of incoming information will be, on the basis of which the notification will be made (sensor data, video cameras, other external information). It is necessary to determine the channels through which the notification will take place: e-mail, SMS, applications or others. Sometimes it is essential to provide multiple access options.

When developing the system, data protection and privacy requirements should be taken into account. It should be ensured that the system complies with the legal framework for data processing and dissemination. In addition, the notification system should be aligned with national and international regulatory enactments, especially those related to crisis management and public protection.

The scalability of the system is a key factor - it must be able to operate even when a large number of users connect simultaneously. Availability and reliability are critical - the system must be available 24/7 and able to withstand emergency situations. There must also be backup mechanisms that ensure operation in the case of system overload or interruption. Integration with other systems is another important technical aspect - the system must be able to work together with other platforms and communication channels.

The system should ensure the dissemination of real-time information, especially in crisis situations, to protect people. Warnings must be accurate, as inaccurate or erroneous information can cause panic or losses. Messages should be clear, simple and understandable, avoiding unnecessary terms.

Cybersecurity is critical because the early warning system can be a target for attacks. It must be protected against cyberattacks, data leaks and sabotage. Physical security must also be ensured to make the system resilient to natural disasters and other threats.

The system must be flexible and adaptable to future threats or technological opportunities. Continuous monitoring and analysis of the system is also necessary to identify problems in a timely manner and implement improvements.

8.1. System components and physical architecture

When analyzing the requirements of the system to be implemented, the existing and planned data sources, volumes and total implementation of the flow system is seen as a system of at least 2 (two) separate servers with separate functions:

- analytical, batch processing processes and visualization data provision services;
- WEB applications and their client and server side business logic.

Server components and their distribution by server, main functions:

- 🔗 **Application server** - Linux OS-based application server with WEB application solution, search engine and business data PostgreSQL DBMS with PostGIS extension;
- 🔗 **Data loading, analysis and graphic data serving server** - Linux OS-based PostgreSQL DBMS with PostGIS extension, scripts for data loading from data.gov.lv, HEC-RAS and appropriate graphic data distribution for the needs of the application server map browser.

It is recommended that all server-side system components are deployed in containers, which allows system administrators to provide system resources that meet the load needs of a particular moment in time. It is expected that system components can operate in load balancing mode, which will mean that several instances of the same component operate simultaneously on several virtual or physical resources, ensuring load sharing and system continuity in the event of a component/resource failure.

The deployment scheme is available in the figure below. As an addition to improving performance, application servers can be separated into one or more servers for distributing graphical data for the needs of the map browser, which is responsible for the graphically displayed GIS data cache. Hosting in the production environment should be adjusted according to the real data volumes and usage characteristics after observations made in the test environment and conclusions about the system performance.

Figure 12. **System architecture**

Data Processing and Services Architecture - includes several components and processes that provide data loading, processing and user access to this data through various applications.

1. Data Loading and Processing:

1.1. Data Sources: data is obtained from external sources, for example, from data.gov.lv and the HEC-RAS server.

1.2. Regular Batch Processing Processes: these processes perform data loading, which includes three main steps:

1.2.1. Cadastre Loading: at this stage, data from the cadastre, which is essential for geospatial analysis, is loaded into the system.

1.2.2. Address Loading: address datasets are loaded and processed.

1.2.3. HEC-RAS Data Loading and Analysis: data obtained from HEC-RAS (a flood modeling system) is loaded and analyzed.

2. Database Management System (DBMS):

1. This loaded data is stored in a database, which is part of the DBMS.

2. From the database, the data is passed to the graphical data service (MVT - Map Vector Tiles), which provides cartographic data to users.

3. Graphical Data Service (MVT): provides processed geospatial data to users in a visualization form that can be used in a user interface (usually as maps or other graphical representations).

4. Application Server:

1. Web Application: this component allows users to access data through web applications. Users interact with the application interface to retrieve information from the database.

2. Search Engine: this module provides data search functionality that allows users to search for specific information in the system.

5. Users: access the system through web applications, where they can view maps, search for data, and retrieve information based on the loaded and processed data.

8.2. HEC-RAS Program

HEC-RAS (Hydrologic Engineering Centre's River Analysis System) is a software developed by the Hydrologic Engineering Centre of the United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE HEC). It is used to perform hydraulic modeling tasks such as river and waterway flood analysis, water flow and flood condition modeling.

HEC-RAS is used for a variety of purposes, including:

- Flood risk analysis and forecasting;
- Hydraulic design and river regulation;
- Sewage and drainage design;
- Flood mapping and management;
- Ecological and environmental flow analysis.

HEC-RAS is a multifaceted hydraulic modeling tool that offers a wide range of functions for flood analysis and early warning systems. The program allows you to perform both one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) modeling, as well as analyze complex flow processes that change over time. One-dimensional modeling is used to analyze river and canal flow, evaluating cross-sectional parameters, water level changes, and flow velocity at various profiles. In turn, 2D modeling provides a detailed representation of surface flow, which is especially important for flood distribution simulations in cases where accuracy and territorial nuances are essential.

HEC-RAS also includes non-stationary flow analysis, which allows you to simulate dynamic situations - for example, the movement of a flood wave or rapid fluctuations in water level. Additional functionality is provided by water quality modeling and transport analysis, which helps to assess the spread of pollution and the movement of sediments in water bodies.

To create a high-quality model, HEC-RAS requires several types of input data. First, information is collected about the geometry of rivers and canals - cross-sections, shorelines, flow paths and

their connections. Also flow data is required, which includes initial and boundary conditions, such as water level and flow velocity values. Meteorological data, including precipitation and other hydrometeorological parameters, provide the opportunity to simulate real-world conditions. The spatial basis of modeling is created using digital terrain and surface models (DTM/DSM).

The modeling results are available in various formats in the HEC-RAS environment. They can be viewed in tables, where detailed information on flow velocities, water levels and other parameters is summarized. The program also allows you to create graphical images, such as flood maps with area overlays, as well as display profile and cross-section graphs, which facilitate flood analysis and solution development.

In addition to the basic functions, HEC-RAS also offers various advanced features:

- 🔹 **Interoperability with other software** - integration with GIS (geographic information systems) and other engineering tools.
- 🔹 **Modeling calibration and validation** - the ability to calibrate models using historical flood data and validate them with real-world observations.
- 🔹 **Automation and scripting** - support for scripting languages such as Python to automate modeling processes.

HEC-RAS is a very powerful and versatile tool for hydraulic and hydrological modeling. It provides engineers and scientists with the tools they need to perform detailed and accurate river and waterway analysis, flood forecasting, and risk management. With its wide range of features and compatibility with other technologies, HEC-RAS is potentially a great tool for any project that requires flood and water flow analysis. However, other tools can also be used if they can provide the same functions and requirements needed for an effective early warning system.

8.3. Data for flood risk modelling

To create an accurate and reliable flood model that can predict the formation and development of floods, it is necessary to collect and integrate several types of data. They cover geographical, hydrological, meteorological and infrastructure aspects, which together allow for the creation of a multi-layered and physically accurate representation of the situation. The main types of data required for flood modelling are as follows:

- 🔹 spatial data (DTM, DSM, geometry, landscape cover);
- 🔹 hydrological data (flow data, water balance, groundwater);
- 🔹 meteorological data (precipitation, weather forecasts);
- 🔹 infrastructure data (hydraulic structures, settlements);
- 🔹 forecast data (climate scenarios, hydrological models).

Spatial data includes digital terrain and surface models (DTM and DSM), which provide detailed information on the elevation of the land surface, buildings and other obstacles that affect the flow of water. DTM is used to determine the direction, speed and inundation of flood waters, while DSM helps to model situations in built-up areas, where buildings and trees significantly affect the movement of water. In addition, information is also needed on the geometry of rivers and canals - cross-sections, shorelines and flow paths - as well as on the landscape cover and the network of existing water bodies, which determine the stability and retention capacity of water in a given area.

Hydrological data form an essential basis for modeling, as they reflect the movement and dy-

namics of water in rivers and groundwater. They include historical and real-time flow data from hydrometric stations, information on precipitation, evaporation, infiltration and basin runoff, as well as observations of groundwater levels. These data allow us to understand how saturated the soil is and what the responses of rivers to intense precipitation or snowmelt are.

Meteorological data is another critical component. Historical and forecast precipitation data - their intensity, duration and distribution - determine the potential for flooding. In addition, short- and long-term weather forecasts are also important, including information on temperature, wind and other parameters that can affect precipitation and snowmelt rates.

Infrastructure data is also needed to model flooding in populated areas. This includes information on hydraulic structures, such as dams, locks and pumping stations, which directly affect the paths and speed of water flow. Data on populated areas, roads and buildings that may be located in potential flood zones are also important.

Forecast data, such as climate models and hydrological forecast models, provide an opportunity to analyze long-term trends and the impact of climate change on the frequency and intensity of floods. Such data is particularly important for long-term planning and improving early warning systems.

Various formats are used for storing and processing data. Spatial data is often in GIS formats, such as shapefiles (.shp) and raster datasets (.tif). Hydrological data from stations are usually provided in tabular or time series format (.csv), while meteorological forecast data often use standardized formats such as NetCDF (.nc) or HDF5 (.h5).

To create an accurate and reliable flood model, it is necessary to integrate all these data types using appropriate software and modeling tools such as HEC-RAS that can process and analyze this diverse information.

Figure 13. *Lielupe RBD 2D geometry*

The Lielupe RBD flood model is a GIS tool developed to analyze and predict flood hazards in the Lielupe RDB. Its goal is to provide a detailed picture of potential flood areas using digital terrain data, hydrological observations and meteorological forecasts. The model was developed with HEC-RAS software, which allows for accurate simulation of water movement and analysis of various flood scenarios.

The model uses several data sources, which ensure its accuracy and reliability. The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) provides information on changes in the elevation of the land surface and helps determine water flow paths. Data on the geometry of rivers and channels — cross-sections, shorelines and flow paths — allows for a detailed representation of the shape and depth of the Lielupe River and its tributaries. Information on landscape cover, including forests, agricultural lands and buildings, helps assess the water infiltration capacity of different types of areas. Hydrometric station data provide historical and real-time flow information necessary for model calibration and verification.

The Lielupe flood model offers several essential functions. It is able to simulate flood situations under various hydrological and meteorological conditions, for example, during intense precipitation or rapid snowmelt. Based on the simulations, the model creates flood maps, which display flooded areas, water depth zones, flow speed and direction. This information allows for risk assessment and identification of endangered areas, infrastructure facilities and settlements that may be affected in the event of a flood. The model functionality also provides scenario analysis, which allows for the assessment of the impact of various conditions and changes — for example, more intense precipitation or reconstruction of river protection systems — on the flood situation.

The model results are presented in easy-to-interpret formats that support planning and decision-making. Flood maps show the potential volume of flooded areas in various scenarios and serve as an essential tool in the development of preventive measures. Hydraulic analyses provide detailed information on water flow velocity, level and depth, helping to understand flood dynamics and their impacts. In addition, the model offers risk zoning, identifying high-risk areas where special precautions and protection solutions are required.

There are two rivers' basins models: Lielupe river and Daugava river – to cover Zemgale planning region territory.

Figure 14. *Lielupe RBD model (left) and Daugava RBD model (right)*

Average full circle operation of the system from modelling to preparedness to send notification is around 7-8 hours. The HEC-RAS performance statistics are:

1. A calculation step of 5 minutes, which provides sufficient time resolution for accurate representation of flood dynamics.
2. Spatial resolution – 4 meter raster, which allows for detailed analysis of the distribution of water flow in the urban environment.
3. Calculation duration – for the period of 9 days, simulating the development and course of floods over a sufficient period of time to cover possible peaks and areas of impact.

The warning and visualization platform is processing and visualizing flood model for 1-2 hours in average.

8.4. Interaction of the early warning system with the flood modeling process

Figure 15. **Simplified EWS operation scheme**

The process depicted in the diagram illustrates the full cycle of flood forecasting and early warning - from data acquisition and preparation to the dissemination of warnings to the public. The process takes place in sequential phases, where each ensures the quality of the next step and data continuity.

The first stage is data acquisition and preparation. Riverbed geometry data is provided by LVÇMC, and terrain information — from LGIA LIDAR data. Both data types are processed using ArcGIS tools, creating accurate geospatial layers and terrain models necessary for further analysis. The input data is manually reviewed, structured and adapted for hydraulic modeling to

ensure their compliance with HEC-RAS requirements.

The next stage is the creation and configuration of the HEC-RAS model. RAS Mapper processes the terrain and geometry layers and converts them into the format used by the HEC-RAS model. The model is supplemented with hydrological data automatically supplied by LEGMC - water levels and discharges - which are necessary for accurate and up-to-date flood forecasting. To ensure the reliability of the model, manual calibration is performed by comparing the simulation results with historical and observed measurements.

Once the hydraulic modeling is performed, RAS Mapper generates maps of water levels and flooded areas. These cartographic materials are created automatically, and they depict the predicted flood coverage, depth and threatened areas, providing clear and visually interpretable information about the possible development of the situation.

Next comes the data exchange and visualization stage. The generated maps and modeling results are transferred to the Early Warning System. Automatic reflection mechanisms ensure that the maps are updated in real time, thus users always have access to up-to-date information.

Additional background and overlay layers are integrated into the cartographic visualization, which improve the map detail and help create a more complete picture of the flood situation in a specific area. These layers ensure more accurate identification of threatened areas and improve the quality of interpretation.

At the end of the process, flood hazard determination and early warning activation are performed. Based on the results of the models, conditions for hazard zones and intensity are defined. The early warning system, using the prepared information, if approved by CP specialist, distributes warnings to residents and involved institutions, informing about possible risks and recommended safety measures.

In this way, comprehensive data processing, forecasting and early warning of floods are ensured using integrated GIS and hydrometeorological data.

9. The developed Early warning system in case of floods

The early warning system for flood risks has been developed as a centralized digital tool, the aim of which is to ensure timely, coordinated and spatially based action in cases of flood threat. The system supports the work of civil protection commissions and local government specialists, allowing for prompt identification of risks, analysis of forecasts, decision-making and initiation of notification of residents and institutions.

9.1. User roles and institutional cooperation in the early warning system

The developed early warning system for flood risks is based on a multi-level user and institutional cooperation model, which ensures both effective system maintenance and operational action in crisis situations. The operation of the system requires the active involvement of several municipalities of the Zemgale planning region, as well as clearly defined user roles with certain responsibilities and functionality.

Involvement of local governments in the Zemgale region

All local governments in the Zemgale planning region, including the city of Jelgava, Jelgava municipality, Bauska municipality, Dobeles municipality and Aizkraukle municipality, can participate in the early warning system. The system has been developed as a shared solution that allows several local governments to operate on a single platform, while maintaining the autonomy and responsibility of each local government for its territory.

The cooperation model provides that local governments agree among themselves on the total maintenance costs of the system, dividing them proportionally (for example, by the number of inhabitants, the size of the territory or another mutually agreed principle). In turn, each local government separately covers the variable costs associated with the notification process, such as the costs of sending short messages (SMS) to the inhabitants of its administrative territory. Such a model ensures both financial transparency and sustainable maintenance of the system in the long term.

User role structure in the system

To ensure a clear division of responsibilities and effective use of the system, several user roles have been defined in the early warning system.

The system administrator is responsible for the technical operation of the entire system at the regional level. This role includes configuring the system, maintaining the access rights structure, as well as the overall stability and development of the system. The system administrator usually operates centrally and provides support to municipal administrators.

The municipal administrator operates within a specific municipality and is responsible for managing users within his institution. He assigns and changes roles, invites new users, manages message templates and monitors the notification process within the territory of his municipality. The municipal administrator ensures that the system is used in accordance with local civil protection needs.

The civil protection specialist is one of the main professional users of the system. This role includes assessing flood risk events, analyzing forecasts, identifying the situation and support-

ing decision-making of the Civil protection commission. The CP specialist uses geospatial data, forecasts and hazard maps available in the system to prepare for possible floods in a timely manner.

The dispatcher is responsible for the operational notification process, especially in cases where manual notification is used. The dispatcher, based on a confirmed event, informs residents using the communication channels defined in the system and monitors the status of message delivery. The civil protection specialist has the same functions to fulfill this role, if the municipality doesn't have MIOC with 24/7 Data operators (dispatchers).

The physical notifier is involved in cases where residents cannot be reached electronically (for example, contact information is not available or there are technical limitations). This role ensures in-person notification at specific addresses, thereby significantly increasing the efficiency and reachability of the system.

The resident is the main end user of the system and at the same time a significant stakeholder. Residents receive warnings about flood risks related to their properties or place of residence and can take timely protective measures. Through other channels residents can also provide feedback or observations, thus contributing to the accuracy and dynamics of the system.

Collaboration approach and benefits

Such a multi-level role and collaboration model ensures that the early warning system is not just a technological solution, but a functioning collaboration platform between municipalities, institutions and residents. Cooperation between municipalities in the Zemgale region allows for more efficient use of resources, while clearly defined user roles ensure quick and coordinated action in flood risk situations, strengthening both institutional preparedness and public safety.

9.2. System functionality

User access and authentication

The use of the system begins with a secure authentication process, which ensures that only authorized persons have access to the system. A municipal employee logs in to the early warning portal, selecting the authentication option as a specialist and entering their access data. Such an approach ensures both data security and a clear division of user responsibilities.

Residents authenticate themselves in the system using a secure state-provided authentication solution (in this case: e-services environment). This allows them to verify their identity while ensuring the protection of personal data. After logging in, the resident gains access to basic functionality related to receiving information and managing notifications.

The authentication mechanism is an essential element of the system, as the system processes sensitive information about threatened territories, residents and the course of crisis situations.

Event overview and situation visualization

A municipal employee can view all events registered in the system in map and list views. Information on active, closed and historical flood events, their spatial location and status is available. This functionality provides an operational overview of the situation at the municipal and regional level.

Figure 16. **Event overview section for a municipal employee**

The event overview section displays all events created within the municipality, grouped by relevance, active events, which include approved and new events, can be viewed by clicking the Active events button [Figure 16, reference 1], closed and rejected events can be viewed by clicking Closed events [Figure 16, reference 2]. Viewing event information can be started by clicking on the event map, or by clicking on the event list [Figure 16, reference 3].

A simplified event overview is available to the resident, which displays active flood events in the territories selected by him or her or in the immediate vicinity. The information is visually understandable and adapted to the everyday user, without including technically complex data.

Figure 17. **Basic view for residents**

Detailed information about an event can be obtained by clicking on the event in the map section, which will open the information section on the left side, with information about the event.

Event management for municipal employees

The event management functionality is the core of the Early warning system. It provides the ability to create, monitor, edit and close hazard events, as well as initiate the notification process related to them.

Events in the system can be:

1. generated automatically, based on HEC-RAS model forecasts,
2. or created manually if information about the hazard is received from other sources.

In the event overview, they are grouped by status, ensuring a clear distinction between active, closed and rejected events. In the map view, the user obtains a spatial overview of both the territory of their municipality and the wider regional situation, which is especially important in cases of inter-municipal flooding.

The event creation or editing function is not available to residents. Their role is to receive information and respond to warnings issued by the municipality.

The system allows a municipal specialist to create new events by defining both their descriptive information and the exact geometry on the map. The available drawing tools (freehand, polygon, circle) provide flexibility in modeling various hazards.

Geospatial accuracy is essential, because the following depends on the geometry of the event:

- 📍 selection of endangered territories,
- 📍 informing the population,
- 📍 resource planning.

Management of exception areas and forecasts

The functionality of management of exception areas allows you to administer land units for which notifications are not made, thus eliminating unnecessary notifications and improving the efficiency of the system.

In addition, the system integrates flood risk forecasts for various recurrence periods (5, 10, 20 and 100 years), which allows the use of the system not only for operational actions, but also for long-term planning and risk assessment.

Notification mechanisms and their flexibility

The system provides several notification types that can be adapted to the specific situation and the capacity of the municipality:

- 📍 automatic notification using predefined or customized notification templates;
- 📍 manual notification by involving a specific dispatcher;
- 📍 physical notification in cases where digital channels are not effective or available.

Management of notification templates allows for the preparation of standardized, yet flexible notifications that can use variable values, thus ensuring both accuracy and quick response.

The notification status view provides transparent information on which territories have already been notified and which still require action, which is especially important in crisis situations with limited time.

Summary

For municipal employees, the system serves as an operational work tool that supports flood risk monitoring, event management, forecast analysis and coordination of the notification process. Timely access to forecast data and spatial information provides an opportunity to identify threats in a timely manner, prepare the necessary resources and ensure targeted action in crisis situations.

In turn, the system provides residents with timely, understandable and reliable information about flood risks in their places of residence or other areas of interest. Flexible notification management, the ability to choose notification areas and available risk information contribute to the awareness of residents and personal preparedness for emergency situations.

10. Stakeholder engagement

The development of an early warning system without the involvement of stakeholders is not possible, as creating an effective solution requires close cooperation with organizations that provide essential information and support. In this case, LEGMC has been involved, which provides critically important meteorological and environmental data. LEGMC's expertise and ability to quickly provide accurate information on weather conditions, environmental hazards and geological changes is a key factor for the system to be able to warn residents and institutions in a timely manner about potential threats, ensuring public safety.

Citizens play a significant role in the development and operation of an early warning system as a group of stakeholders. Citizens are those who are most often directly affected during emergencies, therefore their needs, habits and specifics of information perception significantly affect the design of the system and the choice of communication channels. Citizen participation is manifested both in the active use of warnings in everyday life and in involvement in public consultations, testing events and surveys. Such feedback helps to develop solutions that are understandable, accessible and effective for different groups of society. In addition, citizens, by submitting observations or warning about specific situations, help the system become more dynamic and accurate.

At the same time, the role of local governments and their institutions is particularly important, because they are the first to whom early warning information gives a practical advantage - a longer time to prepare for a possible crisis. Early warnings allow local governments to make an initial assessment of the situation, predict potential risks and identify the necessary resources in a timely manner, such as generators, pumps, transport, temporary accommodation or other critical equipment. This strengthens the ability to take targeted preventive actions, such as directing equipment to potentially threatened areas, monitoring infrastructure or providing additional personnel to services.

The operation of the early warning system is closely linked to local government services, utilities, infrastructure managers, non-governmental organisations and other local structures. The coordinated involvement of these institutions ensures that the system is not an isolated technical tool, but an integrated part of the wider local civil protection infrastructure. At the moment of receiving a warning, the services involved can immediately start working – assess the situation, mobilise personnel and equipment, prepare material and technical resources and inform the population.

Timely action significantly reduces potential losses, speeds up the response process of institutions, and ensures that the municipality is ready to both respond quickly and effectively support residents. This overall strengthens the resilience of the community and its ability to overcome crisis situations with less impact on people and infrastructure.

ANNEXES

MOIC replication checklist

Before the establishment of MOIC		
Decisions to be made	Resolved	Unresolved
What are the digital/smart solutions available in the municipality (video surveillance cameras, monitoring systems, other systems in the municipality that are used by potential Cooperation Partners or that are under the control of the municipality)?		
What is the scope of the municipality's territory that the MOIC is intended to serve?		
What will be the functions and role of MOIC? Is it necessary to expand or narrow the functions of MOIC (compared to Jelgava MOIC)		
Are there any restrictions on granting access to systems available in the municipality for the operation of the MOIC for the provision of operational support to residents and Cooperation Partners?		
Will the MOIC be established as a separate institution or as part of another institution? Where will the MOIC be located?		
What budget is planned for the establishment and annual maintenance of the MOIC?		
Who will be the MOIC Cooperation Partners, based on the established MOIC functions and roles in the municipality?		
What will be the cooperation model with the Cooperation Partners? Will contracts be concluded? Will the operation of the Cooperation Partners be ensured in the shared IT system?		
What municipal regulatory framework and formal decisions are necessary for the establishment of the MOIC?		
How will residents be informed about the activities of the MOIC?		
What is the expected volume of applications (using another MOIC as a reference)? What is the required number of employees?		
Is it planned to establish cooperation with already operating MOICs? If so, on what issues and in what way?		

Creation of MOIC		
Actions to be taken	Done	Not done/ not relevant
Formal decisions must be made and municipal regulations developed for the establishment of MOIC		
The location of the MOIC must be determined		
Personnel selection must be carried out (Head of MOIC, dispatchers, other specialists). If the MOIC is a separate institution, then other personnel (IT, HR specialist, Accountant, Clerk, etc.) must also be selected, the institution must be registered, a bank account must be opened, etc.		
Necessary purchases must be made (office furniture, computer equipment and other equipment, software and licenses)		
The necessary contracts must be concluded (purchase contracts, premises rental/management contracts, social marketing campaign development contracts, telephony, electricity, cleaning contracts, etc.)		
The workplaces must be equipped with office furniture and necessary equipment. The equipment must be connected, programs must be installed and tested.		
Social marketing materials about MOIC activities should be prepared		
Internal rules and systems need to be developed		
The operational services should be informed and a cooperation model should be agreed upon in the context of civil protection (if this is the planned function of the MOIC)		
Contracts must be concluded with Cooperation Partners, the nuances of cooperation must be agreed upon		
Access rights to the shared IT system must be provided to employees of cooperation partners, employees must be trained		
Employee induction must be carried out		
A training or experience exchange trip for employees to an operating MOIC must be carried out (if a positive decision is made on such cooperation)		
A social marketing campaign should be launched for the residents of the municipality		
Applications must be accepted and forwarded		
Results should be monitored and necessary adjustments made to improve the achievable results		